

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION, ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Introduction:

Though systemic obstacles and gender biases have frequently overshadowed women's representation and recognition in a variety of scientific disciplines, women have made significant contributions to science throughout history. Women have had to fight extremely hard to become teachers at the beginning of their careers, whether it is in the highly competitive fields of engineering, medicine, or even economics. Between 1901 and 2023, women were given the Nobel Prize and the Sveriges Riksbank Prize in Economic Sciences in Memory of Alfred Nobel 65 times. Marie Curie is the only woman to have received two Nobel Prizes: the Physics Prize in 1903 and the Chemistry Prize in 1911. This indicates that from 1901 and 2023, 64 women in total have received the Nobel Prize. (<https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/lists/nobel-prize-awarded-women/>) The myth that women are naturally less competent in scientific pursuits is refuted by showcasing the accomplishments of female scientists. Women in science have demonstrated remarkable creativity and intelligence through the work of individuals like Ada Lovelace, the first computer programmer in history, and Rosalind Franklin, who was instrumental in the discovery of the structure of DNA. Their accomplishments demonstrate how important it is to recognize and celebrate the contributions made by women to the advancement of science.

Literature Review:

Analyzing the role of women in Central Asia/Uzbekistan.

Studies reveal that more creative and all-encompassing solutions are produced in scientific domains when there is a diverse leadership pool (Smith, 2019). Women continue to be underrepresented in leadership positions in the global science and technology sectors, despite their vital contributions.

According to historical accounts, women have played a crucial role in scientific advancements, but their contributions are frequently overlooked in favor of those made by men (Johnson, 2021). With the advent of early pioneers like Hypatia of Alexandria and more recent luminaries like Donna Strickland and Frances Arnold, the recipients of the Nobel laureates in chemistry and physics, respectively, the position of women in science has changed dramatically over the ages.

Women's participation in science and leadership roles has historically been restricted in Central Asia, especially in Uzbekistan, due to cultural and societal norms. But according to recent research, there has been a shift in favor of gender equality in the scientific community (Kurbanov et al., 2020). Government programs that support women in science and education as well as global partnerships that advance gender diversity in STEM fields are credited with this shift.

There have been many women achievers too despite hurdles, such as Saida Yusupova from Uzbekistan founder and CEO of Green Business Innovation, who has been inspiring young people and entrepreneurs to "go green"

Methodology:

Utilized national surveys, academic databases, institutional reports, and relevant statistical sources to gather quantitative data on women's participation, representation, and challenges in STEM fields in Central Asia and Uzbekistan. Employed descriptive statistical techniques to analyze quantitative data, and representations such as bar charts, line graphs, pie charts, and scatter plots. Descriptive analysis provided insights into trends, patterns, and variations in women's participation and representation in various fields. Recognized limitations of the methodology, including potential biases in data collection, sample representativeness, and generalizability of findings.

Current Challenges:

Despite advancements in gender equality, disparities persist in STEM fields. Women remain underrepresented in key scientific disciplines and leadership positions, facing barriers such as implicit bias, workplace discrimination, and lack of support networks. The gender pay gap and the "leaky pipeline" phenomenon, where women drop out of scientific careers at higher rates than men, further exacerbate the issue. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach encompassing policy changes, cultural shifts, and institutional support.

Analyzing the role of women in science development. Central Asia/Uzbekistan

Central Asia consists of nations like Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan. It has a long history of scientific research and advancement. Nonetheless, women in Central Asia have encountered particular difficulties when pursuing careers in science, just like in many other areas. Historically, women have been dissuaded from pursuing professional careers and higher education, particularly in scientific fields, by cultural norms and expectations. Despite these obstacles, prominent female scientists from Central Asia have contributed significantly to various scientific fields.

For instance, physicist Dr. Gulya Alimova pioneered advances in the field of spectroscopy in Uzbekistan. Her studies of how light interacts with matter have implications for material science and environmental monitoring, for example. Our knowledge of conservation and ecological management has been enhanced by the pioneering research on the biodiversity of the Kazakh steppe ecosystem carried out by biologist Dr. Roza Kulbayeva in Kazakhstan. But gender inequality still exists in the scientific community of Central Asia, even despite the accomplishments of individual female scientists. In STEM fields, women are still underrepresented, especially when it comes to leadership and decision-making roles. Women's participation and advancement in science are further hampered by cultural barriers, limited support networks, and restricted access to resources. In Central Asia, efforts are being made to advance gender equality in science through programs that support work-life balance, mentorship opportunities, and increased educational access for women. Through networking and mentorship, organizations like the Association of Women in Science and Education in Central Asia (AWISECA) strive to empower women scientists. Notwithstanding these obstacles, women in

Central Asia are rising to prominence in science and are making valuable contributions to both regional development and international knowledge sharing. Central Asia can promote inclusive practices and remove systemic barriers. Through the removal of structural obstacles and the encouragement of inclusive behaviors, Central Asia can fully utilize the rich reservoir of scientific talent within the region, spurring advancements both within and outside of it. fashionable as well as advocacy.

Source: Science Professionals 2022, From NCSES -nation center of science and engineering

Looking at the above data, it becomes evident that there have not been significant changes in the participation of women in the science-related profession, almost steady, lagging behind men, therefore more efforts are required in this direction.

According to the nationwide "Yuksalish "movement, the proportion of women working in leadership positions in the country is 33%. Currently, about 2,000 government and public organizations are headed by women. Women leaders in public administration of Uzbekistan

Some of them are

- Ziroathon Mirziyoyeva - Chairman of the Board of Trustees of the International Public Fund "Zamin".
- Saida Mirziyoyeva - currently the first assistant to the head of state.
- Galina Saidova - Deputy State Advisor to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on socio-economic issues.
- Tanzila Narbaeva - Chairman of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
- Khilola Umarova - Minister of Preschool and School Education.
- Agrippina Shin - Deputy Minister of Preschool and School Education.
- Elmira Basitkhanova - Deputy Minister of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
- Ozoda Parpibaeva - Chairman of the Committee on Family and Women's Affairs under the Ministry of Employment and Poverty Reduction of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
- Madina Mukhammedova (Bukhara, UZB): winner of startup Initiatives by UNDP (2021). A PhD in technical Sciences, her invention relates to Airy Insole for diabetic patients•
- Svetlana Artykova - Deputy Prosecutor General.

How the World looks upon women

Source: UNESCO Institute for Statistics (Women in Science) 2022

Column 1 - "The role of women in society is to be good mothers and wives."

Column 2 - "Things would work better if more women held positions with responsibilities in government/companies."

The above graph shows how people view the role that women should play. Indians, who make up the largest percentage of respondents (79%) believe that women can hold important positions and significantly alter society. Turkish respondents have the same perception (72%). Whereas, people in Russia, have a different perception hence only 34% feel that women need to hold important offices and bring about the changes required in the society.

Recommendations and Conclusions

Gender equality and education are generally strongly related and reinforce one another. In addition to helping individuals and communities, efforts to advance gender equality in education also advance society as a whole. Prioritizing gender equality leads to more inclusive, diverse, and high-quality education. Education also provides people with the means to actively contribute to the advancement of gender equality, thereby starting a positive feedback loop that benefits both gender equality and education.

Key Aspects to Consider • Diversity and Innovation: Women leaders bring unique perspectives and approaches to science based on their life experiences and knowledge. This encourages more diverse consideration of problems and stimulates innovation.

• Role Models: The success of women leaders inspires and motivates the next generation of girls and women to pursue science, breaking down gender stereotypes and expanding opportunities for all. Such role models include the names stated above

- **Creating an Inclusive Environment:** Women leaders actively advocate for equality and inclusion in science, helping to create a more welcoming environment for all participants in the scientific process, regardless of gender, background, or other factors.

- **Solving Global Issues:** Women leaders are actively involved in solving the world's most critical issues such as climate change, health, and sustainable development. Their contributions help find effective solutions and improve the lives of people around the world.

Conclusion

It is necessary to continue to support and promote women leaders in education/science, removing barriers to their path and creating conditions for their further development. This will unlock the full potential of the scientific community and provide more effective solutions to pressing problems facing humanity.

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